

AI4EDU

Conversational AI assistant for teaching and learning

Teacher Mate User Guide

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1. General information

Teacher Mate is an AI-based web application developed within the AI4EDU: Conversational AI assistant for teaching and learning (ERASMUS+, Contract Number: 101087451) project to support teachers in their daily teaching activities, such as lesson planning, creating quizzes and tests, producing teaching materials, assessing students and much more. Designed with user-friendliness in mind, the app aims to improve the teaching experience by simplifying time-consuming and repetitive tasks, allowing teachers to focus more on meaningful interactions with their students.

This guide provides teachers with step-by-step instructions on how to use Teacher Mate effectively. It is a comprehensive resource that helps teachers navigate the platform, exploit and maximize its potential to improve the teaching and learning process.

The Teacher Mate is tailored to the needs of teachers in four countries (Greece, Ireland, Cyprus and Sweden) and supports three languages: Greek, English and Swedish.

2. Create an account and log in

To use Teacher Mate, you must first create an account by following these steps:

1. Visit the [Teacher Mate](#) login page.
2. To specify your preferred language of communication, you should select the globe icon in the upper left corner of the page and then select your country (e.g. Greece, Ireland, Cyprus or Sweden).
3. Click "Create Account" to start the registration process.
4. Fill in the necessary information (Image 1):
 - **Username:** Select a username longer than 3 characters. To help identify your country for research purposes, we recommend that you use a prefix before your username (e.g. CY_username for Cyprus, GR_username for Greece, IR_username for Ireland, and SE_username for Sweden).
 - **Password:** Set a password with at least 4 characters.
 - **Role:** Select Teacher.
 - Read and accept the "**Terms of Use and Privacy Policy**".
5. Click on "REGISTER NOW" to complete your registration.

You'll see a "User created" confirmation message, which means your account was successfully created. You will then be automatically redirected to the login page (Image 1).

To log in, enter the account information you just created and click "SIGN IN".

Sign Up
Enter a username and password to register

Username

Password

Retype Password

Teacher Student

I read and agree with the [Terms of Use and Privacy Statement](#)

REGISTER NOW

Already have an account? [Sign In](#)

Sign In
Enter your username and password to Sign In

Username

Password

SIGN IN

Not registered? [Create account](#)

Interactive learning assistant for Artificial Intelligence
 Explore Artificial Intelligence and learn about its applications, benefits, and risks from its use

Image 1: The new account creation (left) and user login (right) screens in Teacher Mate

3. User Interface

After logging in, you will be taken to the app's home screen (Image 2). In the left column you will find the navigation menu, which includes the various functions of the application:

1. Tools
2. Chat with Teacher Mate
3. Teacher Dashboard
4. My Tests
5. My Content
6. Profile

In the upper right corner of the screen, you'll find the Log out option to exit the app.

The main viewing area shows the available tools of the application.

Image 2: The Teacher Mate home screen.

4. Teacher Mate Tools

This section presents the tools provided by the Teacher Mate and describes their various features and functions. Each tool is specially designed to simplify different aspects of the educational process, helping teachers organize their daily tasks.

4.1 Generate test

The "Generate test" tool allows you to create tests according to your requirements and assign them to your students.

Attention! To create an assessment test and assign it to your students, you must first create a class. Instructions for creating and managing your classes can be found in the relevant [section Teacher Dashboard](#).

Once you have added a class, to create and assign a test to it, go to the "Generate test" tool and fill in the following fields (Image 3):

- **Test title:** Enter a title for the test.
- **Book selection:** Select one of the preloaded textbooks as the source for creating the test, or a new pdf that you have previously uploaded in the "My Content" section.
- **Description of test subject:** Add a brief description of the test topic (e.g. Circulatory System). In the same field you can provide more explanatory information about the test you want to create, such as evaluation criteria for open questions, terms or concepts that you want to cover, etc.
- **Total marks:** Specify the total score for the test.
- **Test duration (minutes):** Enter the time limit for the test.

- **Class/Age of students:** Specify the class/age of your students, e.g. "Grade 6", "K10", "14 years old".
- **Difficulty level:** Select the desired difficulty level of the test between Low, Medium and High
- **Number of open-ended / multiple-choice / cloze (gap-filling) /matching/ true-false questions:** Indicate how many questions from each type you want to include.

Finally, select “Generate”.

Image 3: The home screen of the Generate Test tool

Once the test has been created by the tool, you can modify the title, date of submission, duration and its content (Image 4).

- The "**QUESTION**" column lists the questions created by the tool, which you can edit according to their type.
- The "**OPTIONS**" column shows the available answer options, allowing you to add or remove options as needed.
- The column "**TYPE**" indicates the type of question and cannot be modified.
- The "**CORRECT ANSWER**" column displays the correct answers generated by the tool, which you can review and edit if you wish.
- The "**MARKS**" column shows the breakdown of the score per question, which you can also edit.

To delete a question, select the corresponding trash icon. By clicking the "+" button at the bottom, you can add a new question by selecting its type from the drop-down menu.

Once you have modified the content of the test to meet your needs and preferences, you can assign it to an already created class by selecting it from the "Class" field and then clicking "Assign to students".

Image 4: Screen for editing a generated test

4.2 Text Generator

The "Text Generator" tool is designed to help you create engaging and original texts that can be adapted to any topic, genre or level of learners. With this tool, you can create texts that meet your students' needs, enhancing learning and understanding. The customization capabilities of the tool allow the creation of content that is both creative and effective, helping students develop their reading and comprehension.

To create text, you need to fill in the following fields (Image 5):

- **Student age:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Grade level:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Topic or theme:** Identify the main topic or theme of the text, e.g. "The Water Cycle."
- **Text type or genre:** Specify the text type, e.g. narrative, informative, persuasive, or more specific genre, e.g. letter, newspaper article, blogpost etc
- **Learning objective:** Describe what students need to learn, e.g. "Help students understand the water cycle".
- **Text length:** Set the desired text size, e.g. 250 words, 2 paragraphs.
- **Tone or style:** Specify the style of the text, such as friendly, imaginative, formal, dialogical.
- **Additional criteria:** Add specific requirements for text generation, such as "I want you to include the following key terms: evaporation, rain, cloud" "Use first-person narration."
- **Select a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model and get support for a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Text generator

Create engaging, original texts for students tailored to any topic, genre, or grade level

Student age:
12 years old

Grade level:
Grade 6

Topic or Theme:
The importance of friendship

Text Type or Genre:
Argumentative, article for a school magazine

Learning Objective:
I want my students to have a good example of argumentative essay, with a clear structure and cohesive devices. I want them to understand the format of an article for a magazine (e.g. title, date, author) and the respective style of such a genre.

Length:
350 words

Tone or Style:
Formal but suitable to address peers

Additional Criteria:
Include the importance of friendship in various aspects of human life, include examples, include conditions for a good friendship.

Select resource to chat with
Select...

Generate

Image 5: The home screen of the "Text Generator" tool

Once you select Generate, you will automatically be taken to the app's chat mode (Image 6), where a prompt will be generated based on the information you provided. The tool will then respond with an AI-generated text, following the information provided. You can refine text, ask questions, or give more specific instructions by responding to the tool's response.

Image 6: Prompt (top) and reply (bottom) of the "Generate text" tool

4.3 Concept exploration assistant

The Concept exploration assistant helps you create learning materials that enhance your students' understanding, application and critical analysis of concepts. Through customized questions and suggestions for visual aids, it facilitates active participation and the development of critical thinking in the classroom.

Concept Exploration Assistant

Develop materials to help students understand, apply, and critically explore concepts with tailored questions and visual aids.

Term(s)/Concept(s):
Mitosis and Meiosis

Student age:
14 years old

Grade level:
Grade 9

Level of Detail:
Medium

Number of Examples:
3

Number of Comprehension Questions:
1

Number of Application Questions:
1

Number of Critical Questions:
2

Number of Challenging Questions:
1

Provide the Answers to the Questions:
Yes

Suggested Resources for Visual Aids:
Yes

Special Student Needs:
Students with low academic achievement and learning difficulties

Image 7: The Concept exploration assistant home screen

To create concept explanations, you need to fill in the following fields (Image 7):

- **Term(s), Concept(s):** Type the concept(s) you want students to learn, e.g. "cell", "inflation".
- **Grade level:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. Grade 7, 1st class of upper secondary school.
- **Student age:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Level of detail:** Choose how detailed the explanation of the concept should be depending on the level of your students (e.g. Basic, Intermediate, Advanced).
- **Number of examples:** Type the number of examples you want the tool to provide (e.g. "3").
- **Number of comprehension questions:** Type the number of comprehension questions you want the tool to provide (e.g. "3").
- **Number of practical questions:** Enter the number of practical applications of the concept you want the tool to provide (e.g. "3").
- **Number of critical questions:** Type the number of critical thinking questions you want the tool to provide (e.g., "3").
- **Number of challenging questions:** Type the number of difficult questions you want the tool to provide (e.g. "3").
- **Provide the answers to the questions:** Choose whether you want to include the correct answers.
- **Suggested resources for visual aids:** Choose whether you want to include resources for providing visual aids to students.
- **Special learning needs:** Describe any specific needs, e.g. "Dyslexia".
- **Additional criteria:** Specify additional requirements, such as "Focus on real-world examples."

- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select "Generate", you will automatically be taken to the app's chat mode, where a prompt will be generated based on the information you provided (Image 8). The tool will then respond with a text created through AI to understand the relevant concepts, following the information provided. You can enhance text, ask questions, or give more specific instructions by responding to the tool's response.

Image 8: Concept exploration assistant tool prompt (top) and reply (bottom)

4.4 Create a lesson plan

The Lesson Plan Builder tool is designed to help you create structured lesson plans. It allows you to define learning objectives, organize teaching content, and plan classroom activities.

Επαναφορά πεδίων

Δημιουργία σχεδίου μαθήματος

Δημιουργήστε ολοκληρωμένα σχέδια μαθημάτων με λεπτομερείς δραστηριότητες και εκπαιδευτικό υλικό βάσει εκπαιδευτικών προσεγγίσεων.

Ηλικία μαθητών:
 Προσδιορίστε την ηλικία των μαθητών σας, π.χ. 13 ετών, 13-14 χρόνων.

Τάξη:
 Τάξη: Προσδιορίστε τη σχολική σας τάξη, π.χ. 3η γυμνασίου, Πρώτη Λυκείου,

Μάθημα:
 Προσδιορίστε το μάθημα, π.χ. Βιολογία, Ιστορία, Κοινωνικές Επιστήμες.

Τίτλος μαθήματος:
 Διαλέξτε έναν συνοπτικό τίτλο που να δείχνει την εστίαση του μαθήματος.

Image 9: The home screen of the Create Lesson Plan tool

To create a lesson plan using this tool, you will need to enter the necessary information in the following fields (Image 9):

- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Lesson:** Identify the subject for which the project will be created, e.g. Biology, History.
- **Course title:** Fill in a concise title showing the focus of the course, e.g. "Understanding photosynthesis".
- **Topic:** Identify the specific topic within the broader theme, e.g. "The Water Cycle".
- **Duration in minutes:** Specify the total duration of the lesson in minutes.
- **Teaching objectives:** Clearly state what students should know or be able to do at the end of the lesson, e.g. "Students should be able to analyze primary sources to identify the key events that led to the Polytechnic uprising."
- **Educational approach:** Specify the educational approach that the lesson plan will follow, e.g. "Inquiry-based learning".
- **Number of activities:** Specify the number of activities to include in the course.
- **Type of activities:** Define the type of activities to be included in the lesson, e.g. introduction, practical experiment, group discussion, assessment.
- **Materials and resources:** List all necessary materials, resources and technology for the lesson, e.g. interactive whiteboard, laptops, textbook.
- **Class structure:** Describe how the classroom will be organized, e.g. "Students will be seated in groups for collaborative work", "U shape for class discussions".

- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will automatically be taken to the app's chat mode (Image 10), where a prompt will be generated based on the information you provided. The tool will then respond with an AI-generated detailed lesson plan, following the information provided. You can refine the lesson plan with more specific instructions by responding to the tool's response.

Image 10: Call to action (top) and answer (bottom) of the Create Lesson Plan tool

4.5 Create quizzes

The 'Quiz Maker' tool is designed to create assessment quizzes, saving you time and effort. This tool allows you to create quizzes tailored to your course content and assessment requirements, offering various types of questions to effectively assess your students.

Image 11: The Quiz Maker home screen

To create a quiz using this tool, you will need to enter the necessary information in the fields below (Image 11):

- **Quiz title:** Give a descriptive title to your quiz, e.g. "Newton's Law 2nd Quiz".
- **Subject:** Specify the school subject related to the quiz, e.g. History, Biology.
- **Topic:** Clearly define the topic of the quiz, e.g. Newton's 2nd law.
- **Key concepts:** List the key ideas or concepts that the quiz will cover, e.g. Force, mass, acceleration.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Duration in minutes:** Specify the total duration of the quiz in minutes.
- **Difficulty level:** Select the desired difficulty level of the quiz.
- **Overall score:** Specify the overall score for the quiz.
- **Number of match questions:** Specify the number of matching questions.
- **Number of multiple-choice questions:** Specify the number of multiple-choice questions.
- **Number of answer options for multiple-choice questions:** Specify the number of possible answers to multiple-choice questions.
- **Number of correct answers to multiple-choice questions:** Specify the number of correct answers to multiple-choice questions.
- **Number of gap-filling questions:** Specify the number of gap-filling questions.
- **Number of true/false questions:** Specify the number of true/false questions.
- **Number of open-ended questions:** Specify the number of open-ended questions.
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded

files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will automatically be taken to the app's chat mode (Image 12), where a prompt will be generated based on your input information. The tool will answer with quizzes created with the help of AI, according to the prompt. You can refine the questions or give more specific instructions by answering the tool's response.

Image 12: Call to action (top) and answer (bottom) of the Create Quiz tool

4.6 Scoring and evaluation support

The Grading and Assessment Support tool is designed to automatically evaluate student responses, saving you time and ensuring consistent scoring. This tool can evaluate different types of written responses, providing instant feedback based on the specified criteria.

Επαναφορά πεδίων

Υποστήριξη βαθμολόγησης και αξιολόγησης

Βαθμολογήστε και αξιολογήστε απαντήσεις μαθητών σε εργασίες με βάση εξατομικευμένα κριτήρια και με λεπτομερή ανατροφοδότηση.

Μάθημα:
 Αναφέρετε το μάθημα της εργασίας, π.χ. Ιστορία, Μαθηματικά.

Τάξη:
 Τάξη: Προσδιορίστε τη σχολική σας τάξη, π.χ. 3η γυμνασίου, Πρώτη Λυκείου,

Ηλικία μαθητή:
 Προσδιορίστε την ηλικία των μαθητών σας, π.χ. 13 ετών, 13-14 χρόνων.

Ενότητα/Θέμα:
 Προσδιορίστε τη συγκεκριμένη μαθησιακή ενότητα ή το θέμα στο οποίο βασίζεται η ενασσία. Παράδειγμα: Βυζαντινή Αυτοκρατορία.

Image 13: The home screen of the Scoring and Evaluation Support tool

To use the tool, fill in the following fields (Image 13):

- **Subject:** Specify the school subject related to the task, e.g. History, Biology.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Student age:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Module/Topic:** Identify the specific learning unit or topic on which the project is based, e.g. "Byzantine Empire".
- **Type of task:** Specify the type of task, such as Short Answer, Report, Project, Presentation.
- **Question:** List the exact question or instruction given to students, e.g. "What was Nika's Attitude?"
- **Student response:** Type the exact answer given by the student.
- **Benchmarks and rating by category (optional):** List criteria for evaluation, e.g. "Content accuracy: 5/20, Detail: 5/20, Clarity: 5/20, Completeness: 5/20".
- **Overall score:** State the overall score of the assignment, e.g. 20 points.
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will be taken to its chat function application (Image 14), where a prompt will be generated based on the data you've entered. The tool will respond with a score and evaluation of the provided response, which can be customized or further expanded through interaction.

Image 14: Prompt (top) and answer (bottom) of the "Scoring and Evaluation Support" tool

4.7 Project planning

The Project Design tool is designed to help you create interesting and collaborative projects that promote students' active participation. Through this tool, you can design activities tailored to any topic and class level, enhancing students' creativity, teamwork and critical thinking.

Επιαναφορά πεδίων

Σχεδιασμός πρότζεκτ

Δημιουργήστε ενδιαφέροντα, συνεργατικά πρότζεκτ για μαθητές με βάση οποιοδήποτε θέμα και για οποιαδήποτε τάξη.

Ηλικία μαθητών:
 Προσδιορίστε την ηλικία των μαθητών σας, π.χ. 13 ετών, 13-14 χρόνων.

Τάξη:
 Τάξη: Προσδιορίστε τη σχολική σας τάξη, π.χ. 3η γυμνασίου, Πρώτη Λυκείου, 2ο έτος δευτεροβάθμιας

Μάθημα:

Θέμα:
 Προσδιορίστε το θέμα ή τη θεματική περιοχή εντός του μαθήματος, π.χ. Πολιτισμική διαφορετικότητα, Ο

Μαθησιακοί στόχοι:
 Παραθέστε τις δεξιότητες ή τις γνώσεις που θα αποκτήσουν, π.χ. Ανάπτυξη δεξιοτήτων ομαδικής εργασίας,

Είδος πρότζεκτ:
 Περιγράψτε τη μορφή, π.χ. δημιουργική παρουσίαση, ερευνητικό πρότζεκτ, σκετς, διαδραστική δραστηριότητα

Αριθμός μαθητών ανά ομάδα:
 Υποδείξτε το μέγεθος της ομάδας, π.χ. 4, 5 ή 6 μαθητές ανά ομάδα.

Image 15: The home screen of the Project Plan tool

To use the tool, fill in the fields below (Image 15):

- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.

- **Subject:** Specify the school subject related to the task, e.g. History, Biology.
- **Topic:** Identify the topic or topic area within the lesson, e.g. "The Water Cycle".
- **Learning objectives:** Add the skills or knowledge gained, e.g. "Teamwork skills development".
- **Type of project:** Describe the format of the project, e.g. creative presentation, research project.
- **Number of students per group:** Indicate the size of the groups, e.g. "4-6 students per group".
- **Duration:** Specify the desired duration of the project, e.g. "One week", "2 teaching hours".
- **Additional criteria:** Add additional instructions or requirements, such as "Add comprehension questions."
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will be taken to its chat function application (Image 16), where a prompt will be generated based on the data you've entered. The tool will respond with the description of a project for students with detailed instructions and recommendations for its implementation.

Image 16: Call to action (top) and answer (bottom) of the Project Plan tool

4.8 Development of evaluation criteria

The Assessment Criteria tool helps you define clear and objective criteria for evaluating student work. Through this, you can create custom scoring guidelines, ensuring transparency and consistency in the evaluation process.

Image 17: The home screen of the "Benchmarking" tool

To use the tool, fill in the following fields (Image 17):

- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Job title:** Give a clear and descriptive title for the paper, e.g. "The story of Ulysses".
- **Type of task:** Specify the type of task, such as Short Answer, Report, Project, Presentation.
- **Learning objectives or skills assessed:** Specify the skills or learning objectives you want assessed, e.g. "creative thinking", "creativity".
- **Number of yield levels:** Specify the number of yield levels, such as "4".
- **Attribution level names:** List names for performance levels, e.g. "1. Needs improvement, 2. Satisfactory, 3. Good, 4. Excellent."
- **Evaluation criteria:** Define specific evaluation criteria, e.g. "text coherence", "story coherence".
- **Additional notes for customizing your benchmarks:** Add any specific guidelines or preferences for the benchmarks, such as "Focus on creativity."
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will be taken to the app's chat mode (Image 18), where a prompt will be generated based on the data you've entered. The tool will respond with an evaluation criteria table, organized into performance levels, which can be customized according to your needs. Through interaction, you can modify criteria, add new assessment levels, or customize descriptions, ensuring they meet job requirements and learning objectives.

Δημιούργησε έναν πίνακα κριτηρίων αξιολόγησης για εργασίες μαθητών με σαφή δομή, περιλαμβάνοντας στήλες για κάθε επίπεδο απόδοσης και περιγραφικά κριτήρια για κάθε επίπεδο. Χρησιμοποίησε τα κριτήρια αξιολόγησης όπως τα παρέχω. Σε περίπτωση που δεν παρέχω κριτήρια αξιολόγησης, πρότεινε τα δικά σου κριτήρια με βάση το είδος της εργασίας και τους μαθησιακούς στόχους που παρέχονται.

Τίτλος εργασίας: Σχεδιασμός απλού ηλεκτρικού κυκλώματος αντιστάτων σε σειρά
 Τάξη: Β' Γυμνασίου
 Ηλικία μαθητών: 14
 Είδος εργασίας: Εργαστηριακή άσκηση

Μαθησιακοί στόχοι ή δεξιότητες που αξιολογούνται: Οι μαθητές να σχεδιάζουν απλά ηλεκτρικά κυκλώματα χρησιμοποιώντας τα απαραίτητα ηλεκτρικά στοιχεία (μπαταρία, καλώδιο, αντιστάτες). Οι μαθητές να συνδέουν αντιστάτες σε σειρά. Οι μαθητές να ξεχωρίζουν την παράλληλη σύνδεση αντιστάτων από την σειριακή σύνδεση αντιστάτων.
 Αριθμός επιπέδων απόδοσης: 3
 Ονομασίες επιπέδων απόδοσης (προαιρετικό): Ανεπαρκές, Καλό, Εξαιρετικό
 Κριτήρια αξιολόγησης (προαιρετικό): Τρόπος σύνδεσης αντιστάτων. Συμπερίληψη όλων των ηλεκτρικών στοιχείων
 Πρόσθετες σημειώσεις για την προσαρμογή των κριτηρίων αξιολόγησης (προαιρετικό):

Πίνακας Κριτηρίων Αξιολόγησης για την Εργασία: Σχεδιασμός Απλού Ηλεκτρικού Κυκλώματος Αντιστάτων σε Σειρά

Κριτήρια Αξιολόγησης	Ανεπαρκές	Καλό	Εξαιρετικό
Τρόπος Σύνδεσης Αντιστάτων	Οι αντιστάτες δεν έχουν συνδεθεί σωστά σε σειρά. Υπάρχουν λάθη στη σύνδεση.	Οι αντιστάτες είναι συνδεδεμένοι σε σειρά με κάποιες μικρές στέλεις.	Οι αντιστάτες είναι συνδεδεμένοι σε σειρά άψογα, χωρίς κανένα λάθος.
Συμπερίληψη Όλων των Ηλεκτρικών	Λείπουν βασικά ηλεκτρικά στοιχεία όπως μπαταρία ή	Όλα τα απαραίτητα ηλεκτρικά στοιχεία έχουν συμπεριληφθεί, αλλά μπορεί να	Όλα τα απαραίτητα ηλεκτρικά στοιχεία έχουν συμπεριληφθεί

Συνομιλία με τον Teacher Mate...

Image 18: Call to action (top) and answer (bottom) of the tool "Establishment of benchmarks"

4.9 Design presentations

The Presentation Planner tool helps you create engaging presentations tailored to your course topics. This tool provides you with ideas for effectively structuring content, ensuring presentations are both informative and visually appealing.

Επαναφορά πεδίων

Σχεδιασμός παρουσιάσεων

Δημιουργήστε ελκυστικές και λεπτομερείς εκπαιδευτικές παρουσιάσεις με διαδραστικά στοιχεία.

Μάθημα:

Θέμα:

Ηλικία μαθητών:

Τάξη:

Image 19: The home screen of the Presentation Plan tool

To create a presentation, you must enter the following information (Image 19):

- **Subject:** Specify the school subject related to the task, e.g. History, Biology.
- **Subject:** Clearly define the theme of the presentation, e.g. "The Water Cycle".

- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Aim of the presentation:** Specify the learning objective of the presentation, e.g. "To teach my students the different stages of the water cycle".
- **Key points to include:** List the main subsections or key points to include in the presentation, e.g. 'evaporation, sun, rain'.
- **Number of slides:** Set the desired number of slides, such as "15".
- **Duration in minutes:** Specify the total duration of the presentation, such as "10 minutes."
- **Type of visual aids:** List the type of visual aids for which the AI will suggest sources or creation prompts, e.g. 'graphs', 'maps'.
- **Interaction:** Indicate the interactive elements you want included, such as "questions to discuss", "short quizzes".
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will be taken to its chat function application (Image 20), where a prompt will be generated based on the information you've entered. The tool will respond with a comprehensive presentation, organized into slides, including an introduction, theoretical concepts, examples and exercises. You can then edit its content according to the needs of your course.

Image 20: Call to action (top) and answer (bottom) of the Plan Presentations tool

4.10 Fit text

The "Text Adaptation" tool allows you to shape any text to meet the level, skills and educational needs of your students. Through this feature, you can simplify the language, add explanations or adjust the style and structure of the text to make it easier to understand and accessible for all students.

Επαναφορά πεδίων

Προσαρμογή κειμένου

Προσαρμόστε οποιοδήποτε κείμενο στο επίπεδο, τις δεξιότητες και τις εκπαιδευτικές ανάγκες των μαθητών σας.

Ηλικία μαθητών:
 Προσδιορίστε την ηλικία των μαθητών σας, π.χ. 13 ετών, 13-14 χρόνων.

Τάξη:
 Προσδιορίστε τη σχολική σας τάξη, π.χ. 3η γυμνασίου, Πρώτη Λυκείου, 2ο

Αρχικό κείμενο:
 Αντιγράψτε εδώ το κείμενο που θέλετε να προσαρμοστεί.

Εστίαση σε δεξιότητες:
 Διευκρινίστε τις δεξιότητες στις οποίες θέλετε να δοθεί έμφαση, π.χ.

Image 21: The Fit Text home screen

To use the tool, fill in the following Fields (Image 21):

- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.
- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **Original text:** Copy the text you want to adjust here.
- **Focus on skills:** Specify the skills you want to emphasise, e.g. 'simplifying vocabulary', 'identifying key ideas'.
- **Purpose of reading:** Explain why students will read this text, e.g. "To understand a topic".
- **Additional criteria for customization:** Add additional instructions for customizing the text, e.g. "add comprehension questions", "simplify sentences".
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will be taken to the app's chat mode (Image 22), where a prompt will be generated based on the information you've entered. In response, the tool will adapt your text based on the selected criteria, maintaining its educational content, but in a format appropriate to your students' level. You can further edit the text to better meet the needs of your class.

Image 22: Call to action (top) and reply (bottom) of the Fit Text tool

4.11 Chronological order of events

The Chronological Event Order tool allows teachers to organise fictional, historical or scientific events in correct chronological order. In this way, students better understand the dates, sequences and causal relationships between events. Ideal for teaching history, science and literature, the tool helps to enhance students' temporal perception and analytical thinking.

Image 23: The home screen of the Event Timeline tool

To use the tool, fill in the following Fields (Image 23):

- **Age of students:** Specify the age or age range of your students, e.g. 13 years, 13–14 years.

- **Class:** Identify the class of your students, e.g. 3rd Gymnasium, First Lyceum.
- **List of events:** Enter a list of events in a chronological period or specify a historical period whose events you want to place in chronological order. You can only specify the general theme of the retrospective you want, e.g. "Man on the moon".
- **Context:** Explain the historical/thematic context, e.g. "Events of the time of Justinian in Byzantium".
- **Additional criteria:** Specify your preferences, such as "Highlight key dates and personalities."
- **Choose a source to chat:** Select "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) and get support on a wide range of topics. Alternatively, select one or more preloaded files or a new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section to create content based on the information they contain.

Once you select 'Create', you will be taken to the app's chat mode (Image 24), where a prompt will be generated based on the information you've entered. The tool will then sort the events you entered into the correct chronological order and present them in a clear and organized way. A timeline of successive events will be created, accompanied by brief explanations highlighting their importance and cause-and-effect relationships. Important dates, locations, and personalities, if any, will also be added. Finally, the tool will formulate comprehension questions to enhance the consolidation of the sequence of events.

Image 24: Prompt (top) and reply (bottom) of the Event Timeline tool

5. Chat using pdf file

In all the above tools you can select either "General Chat" to interact with the general language model (ChatGPT-4) or one of the preloaded pdf files, which correspond to selected middle or high school textbooks. You can also select one or more new pdf files, which you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section. Through the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technique, based on the prompt-question you have created, the model first searches for relevant information in your chosen source(s)

(retrieval) and then uses the retrieved information as additional context to create more accurate and relevant answers (generation).

In case we have selected one or more pdf files to produce the answer, then in the reply window we will see open the corresponding pdf we selected (Image 25):

Image 25: Model reply window using pdf file as source

Via the "Select citation" drop-down menu at the end of the model response, we can see up to three reports, which correspond to passages in the source where the model response was based. By selecting any of them, we are transferred to the page where the corresponding report exists. The passage with the recovered information appears marked in yellow.

6. Chat with Teacher Mate

The "Chat with Teacher Mate" feature allows you to participate in real-time conversations with the app. Moreover, it gives you access to the history of conversations, including previous interactions created while using the various tools.

To use this feature, select the "Chat with Teacher Mate" option from the navigation menu. A new conversation will start automatically and the Teacher Mate will welcome you with a message suggesting ways to interact (Image 26). You contact your Teacher Mate by typing your question or message in the specified field. Alternatively, you can use voice interaction by tapping the microphone icon. Say your query slowly and clearly and tap the icon again to stop (the microphone icon will turn dark red while recording is in progress). The Automatic Speech Recognition feature will convert your voice to text. Once the Teacher Mate has created an answer, they will read it aloud. At the same time, you can select the source of Teacher Mate information for each of your conversations, by selecting the corresponding preloaded file or one (or more) new pdf file that you have uploaded yourself in the "My Content" section or the General chat to draw information from the general model.

Image 26: The new chat screen in your Teacher Mate

By clicking the PDF button in the top right corner of the window, you can open the pdf (s) you have selected to search for information and chat. By selecting any of the references at the end of the Teacher Mate answer, you will be redirected to the corresponding page of the pdf from which the answer information was retrieved. The information is marked in yellow. By selecting any book/PDF in the drop-down menu (top right corner of the window), the recovered information from the selected book is displayed (Image 27).

Image 27: Screen of new conversation with Teacher Mate with selection of pdf file(s)

In addition to starting new conversations, you can browse your chat history to look back at previous conversations or visit conversations created during the use of the various tools.

The system automatically assigns a title to each conversation. By selecting the three-dot icon next to each conversation, you can copy the conversation content to the clipboard ("Copy to clipboard"), export the

conversation to a Word file ("Export to Word"), rename the conversation ("Rename conversation"), or permanently delete the conversation ("Delete conversation"). By clicking on any conversation, you can review its content and your interactions with your Teacher Mate. You can also resume any previous conversation by sending a new message.

7. Manage classes

Manage Classes is the central point of managing your classes. From here, you can easily add new classes, track your students' progress, and gain detailed information about their performance.

To create a new class, select Add Class and fill in the fields below (Image 28):

- **Course name:** Give your course a name (e.g. History, Biology). The name can also indicate a subgroup of your physical class, e.g. L2 Greek, Special education etc.
- **Class:** Indicate the grade level of your students, e.g. Grade 7, 1st Lyceum.
- **Number of students:** Set the number of students the class will include. Tip: Add a few extra seats beyond your actual number of students to give you more flexibility, e.g. for trial use.

Once you've filled in the necessary details, click 'Add'.

The screenshot displays the 'Add Class' interface. At the top, there is a button labeled '+ Προσθήκη τάξης'. Below it, a table lists existing classes. The table has two columns: 'Τάξη' (Class) and 'Αριθμός μαθητών' (Number of students). One class is listed: 'M3877: Φυσική, Β' Γυμνασίου' with 20 students. A red trash icon is visible next to the student count. Below the table is a form titled 'Προσθήκη τάξης' (Add Class). The form contains three input fields: 'Όνομα μαθήματος:' (Course name), 'Τάξη:' (Class), and 'Αριθμός μαθητών:' (Number of students). At the bottom of the form are two buttons: 'Προσθήκη' (Add) and 'Ακύρωση' (Cancel).

Image 28: The screen for adding a new class to your Teacher Mate

Once a class is created, the tool automatically generates usernames and passwords for them students (Image 29). Be sure to save this information by clicking the download icon, as it will not be recoverable after closing the window.

Your class will now appear in your class list, with a unique name automatically generated by the tool. You will be able to see the total number of students in the class, as well as delete it if necessary. To manage a class, click its name.

Παρακαλούμε, βεβαιωθείτε ότι έχετε αποθηκεύσει τα δεδομένα, θα χαθούν μόλις κλείσει αυτό το παράθυρο.

Όνομα χρήστη	Συνθηματικό
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_1	KfFS9ixL
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_2	6H251nzA
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_3	RiE0dWUt
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_4	efFm8Lzq
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_5	koBf2I2v
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_6	H7Ikariv
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_7	9zpPCfmf
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_8	MYerUaT0
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_9	W46vTRNj
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_10	n9QcYeg2
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_11	iLGq1AG0
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_12	Kqr5IFLE
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_13	hb8mqMVK
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_14	GGcJBSVm
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_15	7UFSiFa7
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_16	foPrGzWj
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_17	9oNJ9saf
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_18	GD2p4XaY
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_19	dGU8NTwd
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_20	uigWX801
m0805_gr_fysikh_37_b_gymnasiou_student_21	5nrYhCXy

Image 29: The login details of each student of a created class in the Teacher Mate

Once you enter a class, you can see these charts (Image 30):

- **Overall score overview:** Displays the average grade of the class on all tests.
- **Date – Score – Last test:** Shows each student's score on the last test.
- **Date – Time – Last test:** Records the time spent by each student to complete the last test.

Image 30: Class progress charts in Teacher Mate

In the Students window, you can see a summary of each student, including:

- **AVERAGE SCORE:** The average of the student's scores on all tests.
- **LAST TEST SCORE:** The student's performance in the last test.
- **% COMPLETED TESTS:** The percentage of tests completed by the student.
- **PENDING SCORE:** Lets you know if there is a test that hasn't been scored yet.

You can remove a student by clicking on the trash can icon next to their name, or add a student by selecting the "+". To get detailed information about a student, click their name (Image 31). This is yours allows to see:

- The evolution of its score over time "**Completed tests**".
- His/her answers to each question of the last test ("**Answer**").
- The score automatically assigned by AI to each answer ("**AI Score**").
- The total score assigned to each question ("**Total points**").

You also have the option to modify the score automatically generated by AI by filling in the "**Grade**" field and clicking "**Change score**".

The tool also provides personalized feedback to your students through the following fields:

- **General assessment of the student:** Overall assessment of his/her performance in all tests.
- **Test comments:** Feedback based on performance in the last test.

You can edit the content of these fields and provide feedback to the student by clicking "**Update**". By updating this information, students will be able to see their grades and comments on the dashboard of the Study Buddy app, which is the corresponding application of the AI4EDU project for students.

The screenshot displays the 'Individual student assessment screen in Teacher Mate' for a student named 'm3877_fysikh_b_gymnasioy_student_3'. It features a calendar view on the left showing 'Ολοκληρωμένα τεστ' (Completed tests) from Sep to Aug. The main area shows a test titled '07-02-2025 - Τελευταίο τεστ' (07-02-2025 - Last test) with a completion time of 1 minute. The test questions and answers are as follows:

Ερώτηση	Απάντηση	Βαθμός AI	Βαθμός	Σύνολο βαθμών
1. Ποιος από τους παρακάτω κανόνες του Kirchhoff αφορά στην ισότητα των ρευμάτων που εισέρχονται και εξέρχονται από έναν ηλεκτρικό κύκλωμα;	Ο πρώτος κανόνας	4	4	4
2. Σύμφωνα με τον δεύτερο κανόνα του Kirchhoff, το άθροισμα των τάσεων σε ένα _____ κύκλωμα είναι μηδέν.	κλειστό	4	4	4
3. Ταίριαξε μεταξύ των δύο ομάδων Ομάδα Α Πρώτος Κανόνας του Kirchhoff Δεύτερος Κανόνας του Kirchhoff Κανόνας Ισορροπίας Ρεύματος Ομάδα Β Αφορά τις τάσεις Αφορά τα ρεύματα Κλειστό κύκλωμα		0	0	4
4. Περιγράψτε τη σημασία των κανόνων του Kirchhoff στην ανάλυση ηλεκτρικών κυκλωμάτων.		0	0	4
5. Ο δεύτερος κανόνας του Kirchhoff αναφέρεται στην ισοτία του άθροισματος των ρευμάτων σε έναν ηλεκτρικό κύκλωμα.	Λάθος	4	4	4

At the bottom, there are two text boxes for 'Γενική αξιολόγηση μαθητή/τριας' (General student assessment) and 'Σχόλια τεστ' (Test comments). The general assessment box contains the text: 'Ο μαθητής έχει δείξει καλή κατανόηση του 2ου νόμου του Νεύτωνα στις περισσότερες περιπτώσεις. Συγκεκριμένα, οι απαντήσεις στις...'. The test comments box contains: '1: Σωστή απάντηση. Πολύ καλά, κατάλαβες τον πρώτο κανόνα του Kirchhoff. 2: Σωστή απάντηση. Η σωστή λέξη ήταν 'κλειστό'. Συνέχισε έτσι!'.

Image 31: Individual student assessment screen in Teacher Mate

Test results as well as individual feedback are submitted to each student only when you have clicked on the options "Change grade" (under Total grades) and "Update" (under "Test comments" and "General student assessment").

You can test these features by logging out of your Teacher Mate account and logging in as a student using the login details of one of the previously created saved accounts through the Create Test tool. Once logged in as a student, navigate to the "Test" option from the menu, select the test that you want from the relevant drop-down menu and then click on "Get started!" (Image 32).

Image 32: Home test screen for the student in the Study Buddy app

Answer the test questions as if you were a student (Image 33). You can intentionally answer some questions incorrectly to test the tool's features. Finally, click "Submit test". If you wish, you can repeat the process using another student account (sign out and log back in with different student logins).

Image 33: Test questions screen in the Study Buddy app

To view your test results, log out and log back in as a teacher with your personal account. Visit Manage Classes, select the class, then click the student's name to see their test results.

8. My tests

In the "My Tests" section, you can manage older tests and create new ones. In order for the older tests to appear, you must select the class to which you previously assigned it (Image 34: Library of older tests in the "My Tests" section of Teacher Mate Image 34).

You can sort the tests by date of administration ("Date"), title ("Title"), duration ("time") and number of questions ("Number of questions") using the drop-down menu in the upper right corner of the screen.

To delete a test, click the trash can icon next to its name. To manage a test, simply click on its name (Image 4). From there, you can edit the title, submission date, assigned class, duration and content, just like when creating a new test. In addition, you can reassign it to another class.

Finally, to create a new test, click on the "New test" option, located at the top left edge of the screen, and follow the procedure described earlier.

Image 34: Library of older tests in the "My Tests" section of Teacher Mate

9. My Content

The "My Content" section allows you to manage the sources from which the Teacher Mate can draw information to produce responses. From here, you can view the material already uploaded to the app (different textbooks by country) and delete it by clicking on the trash can icon, which appears when you hover over it.

In addition, you can add new material by clicking on the "Add material" option, located at the top left of the screen. Then select a PDF file from your device ("Choose File"), give it your desired name and upload it to the app by clicking "Add" (Image 35). If the upload completes successfully, you'll see the message "File uploaded successfully!" and the file will now be visible in your content. The files you have added are then made available for interaction through the use of any Teacher Mate tool and will now appear in the "Select source to chat" drop-down menu in each tool. In addition, they become available in every free conversation you have with the Teacher Mate.

Image 35: The uploaded files in the "My Content" section of Teacher Mate

10. Profile

You can access your profile information from the navigation menu. In the "Profile" section, you can see your account information, such as your username and country of origin (Image 36).

To change the language of communication, click the globe icon next to the country of origin and select the corresponding country. The available options correspond to the countries involved in the project and include the corresponding preloaded training books for each education system.

Image 36: Screen with a user's profile on Teacher Mate